

Long-Term Outcomes of Cyanoacrylate Glue Ablation for Varicose Veins: A Systematic Review

Section 1: Administrative information

Title: Long-Term Outcomes of Cyanoacrylate Glue Ablation for Varicose Veins: A Systematic Review

Original language title: English

Anticipated start date: 20.04.2026

Anticipated completion date: 30.05.2026

Stage of review at the time of registration: Protocol being developed, data extraction not commenced.

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Review team members:

- Dr. Lalit Kumar Nirwan (Lead reviewer; Guarantor; Conceptualization; Methodology; Writing-original draft; Conflict resolution; Supervision; Project administration; Approval of final draft)
- Dr. Pankaj Banode (Second reviewer; Conceptualization; Project administration- screening coordination; Investigation- literature searches; Writing- review and editing; Validation; Approval of final draft)
- Dr. Harshwardhan Lalit Jain (Third reviewer; Investigation- screening and data extraction; Writing- review and editing; Approval of final draft)

Funding sources/sponsors: None declared

Conflicts of interest: None declared

Collaborators: None

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Section 2: Review Question(s):

Main Research Question:

What are the long-term anatomic closure rates following treatment of varicose veins with cyanoacrylate glue ablation?

Additional Research Questions:

1. What are the long-term clinical outcomes following treatment of varicose veins with cyanoacrylate glue ablation?

2. What is the long-term recanalization rate or failure rate following treatment of varicose veins with cyanoacrylate glue ablation?

3. What is the long-term safety profile following treatment of varicose veins with cyanoacrylate glue ablation?

PICO Framework:

Population: Adults with CEAP C2–C5 varicose veins

Intervention: Cyanoacrylate glue ablation

Comparator: RFA, EVLA, surgery, foam sclerotherapy (where available)

Outcomes: Anatomic closure, recanalization, VCSS, QoL, adverse events

Section 3: Searches and strategy

Sources: Relevant electronic databases will be systematically searched, including but not limited to, PubMed, Embase, Scopus, Cochrane, Web of Science, Science Citation Index.

Search Strategy:

PubMed/MEDLINE Search String

#1 Cyanoacrylate Concepts

(“Cyanoacrylates”[Mesh] OR “Enbucrilate”[Mesh] OR “Tissue Adhesives”[Mesh] OR
Cyanoacrylate[tiab] OR “cyanoacrylate glue”[tiab] OR “N-butyl cyanoacrylate”[tiab] OR
“n-butyl cyanoacrylate”[tiab] OR “butyl cyanoacrylate”[tiab] OR
“2-octyl cyanoacrylate”[tiab] OR “ethyl cyanoacrylate”[tiab] OR
VenaSeal[tiab] OR VenaSeal™[tiab] OR VariClose[tiab] OR VenaBLOCK[tiab] OR
“glue ablation”[tiab] OR “cyanoacrylate embolisation”[tiab] OR
“cyanoacrylate embolization”[tiab] OR “cyanoacrylate closure”[tiab] OR
“endovenous glue”[tiab] OR “non-thermal ablation”[tiab] OR
“nonthermal ablation”[tiab] OR “non-tumescent ablation”[tiab] OR
“nontumescent ablation”[tiab])

#2 Venous Insufficiency Concepts

(“Varicose Veins”[Mesh] OR “Venous Insufficiency”[Mesh] OR “Saphenous Vein”[Mesh]
OR
“varicose vein”[tiab] OR “varicose veins”[tiab] OR “venous insufficiency”[tiab] OR
“chronic venous insufficiency”[tiab] OR CVI[tiab] OR “venous reflux”[tiab] OR
“saphenous vein”[tiab] OR “great saphenous vein”[tiab] OR “small saphenous vein”[tiab]
OR

“GSV”[tiab] OR “SSV”[tiab] OR “truncal vein”[tiab] OR “truncal veins”[tiab] OR
“superficial venous incompetence”[tiab] OR “venous incompetence”[tiab] OR
“lower extremity varicose veins”[tiab] OR “leg varicose veins”[tiab] OR
“CEAP”[tiab] OR “venous disease”[tiab])

#3 Long-Term Follow-Up Concepts

(“Follow-Up Studies”[Mesh] OR “Time Factors”[Mesh] OR “Treatment Outcome”[Mesh] OR
“long-term”[tiab] OR “long term”[tiab] OR “longterm”[tiab] OR
“three-year”[tiab] OR “3-year”[tiab] OR “36-month”[tiab] OR “36 month”[tiab] OR
“five-year”[tiab] OR “5-year”[tiab] OR “60-month”[tiab] OR “60 month”[tiab] OR
“eight-year”[tiab] OR “8-year”[tiab] OR “96-month”[tiab] OR
“follow-up”[tiab] OR
“durability”[tiab] OR “recanalization”[tiab] OR “recanalisation”[tiab] OR
“occlusion rate”[tiab] OR “closure rate”[tiab] OR “patency”[tiab] OR “vein closure”[tiab])

Web of Science Search String

TS=((cyanoacrylate* OR “n-butyl cyanoacrylate” OR “butyl cyanoacrylate” OR “2-octyl
cyanoacrylate” OR VenaSeal OR VariClose OR VenaBLOCK OR “glue ablation” OR
“cyanoacrylate embolization”) AND (“varicose vein*” OR “venous insufficiency” OR
“chronic venous insufficiency” OR CVI OR “saphenous vein*” OR GSV OR SSV) AND
 (“long-term” OR “3-year” OR “5-year” OR “8-year” OR “follow-up”))

Scopus and Embase Search String

('cyanoacrylate'/exp OR 'cyanoacrylate derivative'/exp OR 'n butyl 2 cyanoacrylate'/exp OR '2
octyl cyanoacrylate'/exp OR 'tissue adhesive'/exp OR 'cyanoacrylate glue'/exp OR
cyanoacrylate:ti,ab OR 'n-butyl cyanoacrylate':ti,ab OR 'butyl cyanoacrylate':ti,ab OR '2-octyl
cyanoacrylate':ti,ab OR VenaSeal:ti,ab OR VariClose:ti,ab OR VenaBLOCK:ti,ab OR 'glue
ablation':ti,ab OR 'cyanoacrylate embolization':ti,ab OR 'cyanoacrylate closure':ti,ab OR 'non-
thermal ablation':ti,ab) AND ('varicosis'/exp OR 'chronic vein insufficiency'/exp OR
'saphenous vein'/exp OR 'great saphenous vein'/exp OR 'varicose vein':ti,ab OR 'varicose
veins':ti,ab OR 'venous insufficiency':ti,ab OR 'chronic venous insufficiency':ti,ab OR
CVI:ti,ab OR 'saphenous vein':ti,ab OR GSV:ti,ab OR SSV:ti,ab) AND ('long term care'/exp
OR 'follow-up'/exp OR 'treatment outcome'/exp OR 'long-term':ti,ab OR '3-year':ti,ab OR '5-
year':ti,ab OR 'follow-up':ti,ab OR durability:ti,ab OR recanalization:ti,ab OR 'closure
rate':ti,ab)

Limit Setting

Publication date: January 1, 2020 – April 15, 2026

Language: English

Species: Humans

Publication types: Journal articles (excluding conference abstracts, editorials, letters, commentaries)

Supplementary searches:

1. ClinicalTrials.gov for unpublished or ongoing trials.
2. Forward citation tracking.

Section 4: Types of studies to be included:

Study Designs: Prospective and retrospective cohort studies and randomized controlled trials.

Inclusion criteria:

- Prospective or retrospective cohort studies or randomized controlled trials.
- Published from 01.01.2020 to 15.04.2026.
- Published in English language.
- Full text available.
- Follow-up period of 3 years or more.
- Studies with more than 50 patients.

Exclusion criteria

- Case reports or case series.
- Reviews, editorials, conference abstracts and commentaries.
- Animal or in vitro studies.
- Studies including cyanoacrylate glue for non-venous indication (like aneurysms).
- Studies not in English language or where full text article is not available.

Section 5: Condition or Domain under study

Chronic venous insufficiency or varicose veins is a progressive condition characterized by inadequate venous return from the lower extremities due to structural or functional abnormalities of the venous system. Surgical stripping is the definitive treatment but is associated with significant morbidity and recurrence. Therefore, alternative minimally invasive treatment modalities have been developed. Thermal ablation methods have become the gold standard but are associated with thermal injury to the surrounding tissues and requirement of tumescent anesthesia, increasing the recovery time. Cyanoacrylate glue is a recently developed non-thermal treatment modality. This review aims to systematically evaluate the long-term efficacy and safety of cyanoacrylate glue ablation.

Rationale for focus on long-term follow-up studies: This focus is justified as cyanoacrylate glue ablation is a relatively recent treatment modality, so studies for long-term are required.

There may be instances of late recanalization which may be missed in reviews with shorter follow-up. There is a need for high-quality evidence for long-term efficacy and safety of cyanoacrylate glue ablation.

Section 6: Participants/Population:

Inclusion criteria: Adult patients (aged 18 years or more) of either gender, diagnosed with Clinical-Etiological-Anatomical-Physiological (CEAP) classification C2 to C5.

Exclusion criteria: Patients with C1 or C6 class of CEAP classification, pregnancy or breastfeeding women, aneurysm of target vein (more than 12-15 mm) or peripheral artery disease (ankle-brachial index less than 0.8).

Section 7: Intervention(s), Exposure(s)

Primary Exposure: Cyanoacrylate glue ablation using any commercially available device.

Procedure characteristics:

- Non-thermal, non-tumescent technique
- Ultrasound-guided puncture and sheath placement
- Catheter advancement to 2-5 cm distal to saphenofemoral or saphenopopliteal junction
- Cyanoacrylate injection with simultaneous external compression
- No requirement for tumescent anesthesia (by definition of the technique)
- Post-procedure compression stockings may or may not be used (will be recorded as a variable)

Comparator(s)/Control: Where available, comparator groups will include radiofrequency ablation (RFA), endovenous laser ablation (EVLA), surgical stripping, or ultrasound-guided foam sclerotherapy. Comparative analyses will be performed where appropriate; otherwise, single-arm outcome synthesis will be undertaken. Single arm studies shall be included as the hypothesized outcome of this review is long-term efficacy and safety of cyanoacrylate glue ablation.

Section 8: Outcomes:

Primary Outcomes: It will be assessed by anatomic closure rate (Complete occlusion) of the treated vein segment with no clinically significant recanalization (defined as absence of flow within the treated vein segment on duplex ultrasound, as per individual study definitions; definitions will be extracted and harmonized where feasible) at follow-up of 3 or more years post-procedure. Kaplan-Meier freedom from recanalization shall be included (wherever reported). Time-to-event outcomes such as Kaplan–Meier estimates of freedom from recanalization will be extracted and analysed where reported. Long-term follow-up is defined as ≥ 3 years.

Secondary Outcomes: It will include long-term clinical improvement and safety profile of cyanoacrylate glue ablation.

- Clinical improvement: Change in disease severity from baseline Venous Clinical Severity Score (VCSS) ≥ 3 years post-procedure.
- Quality of life: Change in disease-specific and generic QoL Aberdeen Varicose Vein Questionnaire (AVVQ), EuroQol 5-Dimension (EQ-5D), or validated equivalent ≥ 3 years post-procedure.
- Recanalization rate at follow-up of 3 years or more.
- Adverse events: Any untoward medical occurrence, either serious, death or minor events at all time points with focus on follow-up of 3 or more years.

Section 9: Data extraction, assessment and synthesis

Data extraction: Data will be extracted for all the primary and secondary outcome parameters independently by two Reviewers and any disagreements will be solved by consensus. In case, if it is unresolved, a third Reviewer will adjudicate. In case of missing or unclear data, the corresponding authors of the study will be contacted for a maximum of two times.

Risk of bias assessment: For non-randomized studies

Tool	Newcastle-Ottawa scale
Domains	Selection (0–4 stars), Comparability (0–2 stars), Outcome (0–3 stars)
Quality rating	High quality (≥ 7 stars), Moderate quality (5–6 stars), Low quality (≤ 4 stars)
Process of assessment	Two reviewers independently assess; consensus for final rating

For randomized controlled trials, it will be done by Cochrane Risk of Bias 2.0 (RoB 2) tool by two independent reviewers. The following domains will be evaluated:

D1: Bias arising from the randomization process

D2: Bias due to deviations from intended interventions

D3: Bias due to missing outcome data

D4: Bias in measurement of the outcome

D5: Bias in selection of the reported result

Each domain will be judged as “Low risk,” “Some concerns,” or “High risk.” An overall risk of bias judgement will be assigned as:

- Low risk: Low risk in all domains
- Some concerns: Some concerns in at least one domain but not high risk in any domain
- High risk: High risk in at least one domain or some concerns in multiple domains

Sensitivity analyses will be conducted by excluding studies with high risk of bias and low methodological quality.

Protocol peer review: The protocol was peer reviewed independently by an interventional radiologist and public health specialist for relevance of research question and relevance of outcomes. This helped us strengthen the eligibility criteria, search strategy and adherence to PRISMA guidelines enhancing the quality of the review.

Meta-analysis: Meta-analysis will be performed if studies are sufficiently homogeneous in terms of population, intervention, and outcome definitions; otherwise, a narrative synthesis will be conducted. Heterogeneity will be assessed using the I² statistic, interpreted as follows: 0–40% (low), 30–60% (moderate), 50–90% (substantial), and >75% (considerable heterogeneity). Subgroup analyses will be performed based on duration of follow-up (3–5 years vs >5 years), type of vein treated (GSV vs SSV), type of cyanoacrylate device used and study design (RCT vs observational).

Narrative synthesis: A narrative synthesis will be conducted in accordance with the Synthesis Without Meta-Analysis (SWiM) reporting guideline (as per BMJ 2020). Findings will be presented descriptively with summary tables, data ranges, weighted averages (where denominators are clearly defined), and incidence rates.

Certainty of Evidence Assessment: The certainty of evidence will be assessed using the Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) approach for key outcomes.

Domain	Assessment
Risk of bias	NOS scores
Inconsistency	Based on variability in effect estimates across included studies
Indirectness	Based on applicability to target population
Imprecision	Based on sample sizes and confidence intervals
Publication bias	Assessed qualitatively and, where ≥ 10 studies are available, using funnel plots and Egger's test

Section 10: Justification for a new systematic review

Based on search of various databases, we identified some studies with similar objectives. However, most of them are limited to short-term and medium-term follow-up with little or no evidence about the long-term durability of treatment of varicose veins with cyanoacrylate glue ablation. As cyanoacrylate glue is a relatively recent non-thermal ablation agent for the treatment of varicose veins, robust long-term evidence remains limited. High-quality, long-term data is required for clinicians and patients to make informed decisions about selection of treatment. Therefore, this systematic review is designed to assess the long-term efficacy and safety (follow-up of 3 years or more) following treatment of varicose veins with cyanoacrylate glue ablation.

The search of PROSPERO did not identify any currently registered or completed reviews for long-term follow-up following treatment of varicose veins with cyanoacrylate glue ablation with specific exclusion of case series and case reports.

Section 11: Dissemination plans:

The protocol will be registered with PROSPERO, and data will be made available upon reasonable request to the research community. For the clinical audience, the findings will be submitted for publication in an indexed peer-reviewed medical journal. Presentation of the data at National Conference of the Speciality shall be considered.

Section 12: Keywords

Category	Keywords
Condition	Varicose veins, chronic venous insufficiency, venous insufficiency, CEAP, leg varicose veins
Population	Adult patients, men, women, CEAP C2-C5, patients with varicose veins, patients with venous insufficiency
Study Design	Systematic review, prospective, retrospective, cohort study, randomized controlled trial
Outcomes	Anatomic closure, closure rates, occlusion, recanalization, VCSS, symptom relief, clinical improvement, quality of life, adverse events, complications, long-term follow-up
MeSH terms	Cyanoacrylates, tissue adhesives, therapeutic embolization, varicose veins, chronic venous insufficiency, treatment outcome, follow-up studies, recurrence, postoperative complications, humans, adult

Section 13: Review Team Contact Details:

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Section 14: Declarations

Field	Response
Conflicts of interest	None declared
Funding	None declared
Registration status	No previous registration
Ethics approval	Not required
Amendments	Any amendment shall be documented with date, details and justification in the final publication

Section 15: Support for this review: None. Technical support: not applicable.